

INTRODUCING MATHEMATICAL CONCEPTS USING HATS AND COINS PUZZLES

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Abstract: *The aim of this note is to show how useful are some basic mathematical concepts from algebra and coding theory: complete set of residues, linear codes and parity checks for solving some popular puzzles involving hats and coins. We introduce: the sets of residues for solving the “hats in a circle puzzle; the binary linear codes for solving the “fake coin puzzle”; and the parity check method for solving the “hats in a line” puzzle.*

Keywords: *coin; hat; puzzle; residue; linear code; parity check*

We will introduce three puzzles and solve them using various mathematical tools. As we will see in the second and third ones, the number parity (being even 0 or odd 1) is very useful in different settings. The connection to the first puzzle is obvious since using parity (either 0 or 1) is the same as using the set of residues (but modulo 2), which we will do in the first puzzle. All three puzzles can be found on popular video channels on YouTube. For example, the first puzzle can be found in [5], and the third in [3]. More information on using linear codes for solving coin puzzles can be found in [3, p. 214] and the references therein.

I. The “hats in a circle” puzzle

Definition: A set of numbers $a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1} \pmod{n}$ form a **complete set of residues**, if there is a congruence $a_i \equiv i \pmod{n}$ for $i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$.

A complete set of residues is a useful tool in mathematics, and it can be used to solve the following hats puzzle:

There are n players (prisoners) and n types of hats. The players form a circle, and the game master puts a random hat on each player’s head. Everyone sees the hats all others have and does not know his hat type. The goal is for each player to

guess his hat type. Is there a strategy that guarantees that at least one of the players can guess correctly?

The unexpected answer is **Yes**, and in fact, the only way for at least one player to succeed is to force exactly one of the players to be correct. In order to do this, we need to ensure that there are no overlaps between predictions. This can be achieved with the help of the following statement:

Theorem: If each player guesses the number g_j , such that $g_j + (S - h_j)$ gives residue j forming a complete set of residues modulo n , then exactly one of the players is right.

Proof: Denote hat types by $0, 1, \dots, n-1$. Let j -th player, $0 \leq j \leq n-1$, receives a hat numbered $0 \leq h_j \leq n-1$ and

$S = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} h_i$ be the total sum of the hats. The strategy is for each

player to guess his hat number g_j , so that it sets the total sum he sees to a residue j modulo n , thus $g_j + (S - h_j) \equiv j \pmod{n}$.

Since everybody sets the total sum he sees to a different residue modulo n , their guesses form a complete residue system $\{0, 1, \dots, n-1\}$. If we assume no one's correct, then $g_j \equiv h_j - S + j \not\equiv h_j$, which leads to $S - j \not\equiv 0 \pmod{n}$ for all $0 \leq j \leq n-1$. This is a contradiction, since the set $\{j\}, 0 \leq j \leq n-1$ forms a complete residue system, so does $\{S - j\}, 0 \leq j \leq n-1$. Therefore, at least one player guesses correctly. In fact, the completeness of the system $\{S - j\}, 0 \leq j \leq n-1$ guarantees that exactly one of the residues is 0. Then one and only one of the players guesses correctly: $g_k \equiv h_k$.

II. The “find the fake coin” puzzle

We continue with an introduction to basic concepts from information theory and, in particular, from the theory of error-correcting codes. For an in-depth introduction to these topics,

we refer the reader to [2]. As we will see shortly, a “fake” coin can be interpreted as an error in the transmission.

Definition: A linear $[n, k]$ **code** C is a k -dimensional subspace of the vector space \mathbb{F}_q^n , where \mathbb{F}_q denotes the finite field of $q = p^s$ elements, for a prime number p .

Each element of the code C , called codeword, is a n -tuple $(a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1})$ with elements from \mathbb{F}_q . Since we will deal with fake coins, we can focus our attention on the binary field $\mathbb{F}_2 = \{0, 1\}$, thus we will use binary linear codes. This stems from the following interpretation: Like with propositions (where the true ones have a logical value of 1, and the false ones have a value of 0), we can assume that all “real” coins are denoted by 1, and the “fake” is a 0 (or vice versa).

When transmitting information (or vectors in our case), we do this in binary form, so every error in the channel results in one or more binary flips (transferring 0 to 1 and vice versa) applied to the vector. This is true for the two types of coins (real and fake), and if we have more diversity, we have to use codes over fields with a larger number of elements. But we continue by describing how linear codes operate and have the ability to find and correct errors in transmission. Firstly, every code has a **generator matrix** G of type $k \times n$ consisting of binary vectors forming the basis of the code C . The purpose of G is to map every binary k -tuple $u = (u_1, \dots, u_k)$ into a codeword $v = (v_1, \dots, v_n)$ by applying the generator matrix $v = uG$. The codeword v is transmitted and depending on the code properties a number of errors, denoted by t , can be corrected.

To find this number, we need to introduce the concept of **Hamming distance** $d(x, y)$ in \mathbb{F}_2^n , which is defined as the number of coordinate positions the two binary n -tuples x and y differ. Every element $x \in \mathbb{F}_2^n$ has his *weight* $wt(x)$, which is the number of its nonzero coordinates. To find the **minimum distance** (also termed the **minimal weight**) of the code C , we can use the formula $d(x, y) = wt(x - y)$, and simply use the

minimal weight of the nonzero vectors in C . Thusly, we arrive at the third important parameter d of every linear code, and we say that C is a $[n, k, d]$ code. Denoting by $\lfloor w \rfloor$ the greatest integer less than or equal to w , from the minimum distance we calculate the number of errors $t = \left\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \right\rfloor$ the code can correct.

A parity check matrix H for C is a $(n-k) \times n$ matrix such that $C = \{x \in \mathbb{F}_q^n \mid Hx^T = 0\}$. **The syndrome** of a vector $x \in \mathbb{F}_q^n$ with respect to the parity check matrix H is the vector in \mathbb{F}_q^{n-k} defined by $\text{syn}(x) = Hx^T$. Sending a codeword x from C , in case of no errors occurred, obviously, its syndrome should be zero. If we have the error vector $e \in \mathbb{F}_q^n$, we have received $x + e$. When the weight of the error $\text{wt}(e)$ is less than t , applying the syndrome $\text{syn}(x + e) = \text{syn}(x) + \text{syn}(e) = \text{syn}(e)$, we can find the error and correct it by $x = y - e = (x + e) - e$.

The puzzle we will solve using linear codes is the following: There are 8 coins, one of which is fake, but no information is given as to whether it is lighter or heavier than the rest. Using simple scales, what is the minimal number of weighings we need in order to always find the fake coin if we assume that we have to set the procedure for checking beforehand regardless of the results? The right answer is four weighings. To explain why and how, we will use the $[8, 4, 4]$ linear binary code C with generator matrix

$$G = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \text{ which can correct a single}$$

error. The parity check matrix of this code is

$$H = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \text{ We should mention that the}$$

code C , called extended Hamming code, arises from the perfect $[7, 4, 3]$ Hamming code (see [1]) adding the 8th column as a parity-check of the first seven.

Assuming we encode the all-one vector $(1,1,1,1)$, we get the all-one codeword $y = (1,1,1,1,1,1,1,1)$ (for a moment we can think of this as all 8 coins are real). Then we get one error (the fake coin) flipping one of the coordinates of y . The syndrome of every possible fake coin position (by the formula these are the columns of H) is given in Table 1.

Table 1: The pairs $(p, \text{syn}(p))$ for fake coin position p

1: 0111	2: 1011	3: 1101	4: 1110
5: 1000	6: 0100	7: 0010	8: 0001

It doesn't matter what coins are on either side of the scales, as long as we have two on each. We have the following algorithm (arising from the rows of G) using four tries: 1st: coins 1, 6, 7, and 8; 2nd: 2, 5, 7, and 8; 3rd: 3, 5, 6, and 8; 4th: 4, 5, 6, and 7. Considering 1 as the scales are in equilibrium and 0 otherwise, the fake coin number can be correctly identified from Table 1. The correctness of this procedure can be also explained by the following system of four equations (which are true if all coins are real):

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + x_6 = x_7 + x_8 \\ x_2 + x_5 = x_7 + x_8 \\ x_3 + x_5 = x_6 + x_8 \\ x_4 + x_5 = x_6 + x_7. \end{cases}$$

If numbers 1, 2, 3 or 4 is fake we have inequality in the corresponding position in the system (the same as the first row

of Table 1). If, for example, we have 5 as fake, then the scales will show (1, 0, 0, 0) which correctly solves this case.

The power of the linear codes is that this puzzle can be generalized for more coins, and we can always get a similar procedure, as long as all codewords of C have even weight. This is due to the fact that we need to have an equal number of coins on both sides of the scales.

III. The “hats in a line” puzzle

The next hat puzzle is stated as follows: There are n players in a line, each having a black or red hat. The first player sees all others' hats but cannot see his own. The second sees all next in line but not his hat or the first player's, and so on. Everybody has to guess his hat color correctly. How many of the player can guess correctly? Paradoxically, the right answer is $n - 1$, which is obviously the maximum since the first player has 50% chance of guessing right. Let see what strategy the players can deploy to achieve success.

We can think of the two hats color as binary numbers: 0 for black, and 1 for red. Denote the players by p_0, p_1, \dots, p_{n-1} , and their hat colors as $h_0, h_1, \dots, h_{n-1} \in \{0,1\}$. We have a binary n -tuple $(h_0, h_1, \dots, h_{n-1})$. Obviously, the first player p_0 has no information about his hat's color, so his sole role is to work as the information feedback supplier. In this case he can give the next in line the correct parity check information (and his hat color suggestion h_0 obviously true only in 50% of the cases),

which is $h_0 = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} h_i \pmod{2}$. In other words, he simply has to convey to the next player the oddity of the remaining players' hats.

Next player p_k for $1 \leq k < n - 1$ has the feedback parity-check information from the previous player: $h_{k-1} = \sum_{i=k}^{n-1} h_i \pmod{2}$ as well as the information he sees (the oddity of the sum of all

following players' hats) $g_k = \sum_{i=k+1}^{n-1} h_i \pmod{2}$, so he can find and say his hat color (we can treat it as a binary error) by simply adding both numbers together. Since addition and subtraction in \mathbb{F}_2 is the same operation, he can compute and convey his hat color as follows:

$$h_k = \sum_{i=k}^{n-1} h_i - \sum_{i=k+1}^{n-1} h_i = \sum_{i=k}^{n-1} h_i + \sum_{i=k+1}^{n-1} h_i = h_{k-1} + g_k \pmod{2}.$$

Paradoxically, the strategy for the last player is the same regardless of the fact that he doesn't see any further hats. His hat color h_{n-1} is exactly the sum of all previous players' colors: $h_{n-1} = h_0 + h_1 + \dots + h_{n-2}$. This follows from the equation $h_0 = h_1 + \dots + h_{n-2} + h_{n-1}$ after transferring all summands $h_i, 1 \leq i \leq n-2$ to the left-hand side of the equation, again using the fact that we have no negatives in \mathbb{F}_2 .

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